

A helping hand when drowning: The versatile role of ethylene in root flooding resilience

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ABSTRACT

Ethylene plays a very important role as a stress signal for flooded plants, triggering a range of morphological and metabolic changes that help plants acclimate and survive these conditions. The present review surveys the current knowledge on the mechanisms underlying ethylene-dependent survival responses to waterlogging. We untangle the complexity of waterlogging signaling and response, focusing on root and shoot acclimation strategies mediated by ethylene. We describe how ethylene can have versatile roles in waterlogging tolerance, acting both as a local and long-distance signal during soil flooding and reoxygenation. We discuss the internal and external factors contributing to ethylene versatility in waterlogging responses. Finally, we highlight the current challenges and future research directions in the field, focusing not only on ethylene-mediated responses but also on flooding research applications in crop improvement.

1. Introduction

Flooding events are highly detrimental to most terrestrial plants. Both soil waterlogging and submergence can negatively affect plant performance, impacting species distribution and reducing crop yields. The damaging effects of flooding can be largely attributed to the highly reduced rates of gas diffusion in water. Flooded plant tissues will therefore experience hampered gas exchange with the environment. The consequent effects on CO₂ and O₂ availability can impair efficient photosynthesis and aerobic energy generation and ultimately lead to plant mortality (Zhang et al., 2022b; Zhang et al., 2022a; Zhou et al., 2020).

Plant roots are the most prone to flooding. Water-saturated soils are rapidly depleted of oxygen resulting in a reduction in oxygen supply to the root (Fig. 1). Hypoxia alters soil pH and redox potential, inhibits nitrogen fixation, and causes the accumulation of molecules that can be toxic to roots including fermentation end-products and reduced metal ions (Goud et al., 2022; Jung et al., 2008). Waterlogging also modifies soil compaction and the microbial composition of the rhizosphere while enhancing root-microbial competition for nutrient and oxygen uptake. Hypoxic roots will experience an energy imbalance and excessive generation of redox-active reactive oxygen species (ROS) and nitric oxide

(NO) can cause tissue injury. Waterlogging is thus a compound stress that will impair normal root development and functioning. Ultimately the lack of sufficient mineral and water uptake will also impact the shoots and whole plant homeostasis leading to a cascade of events including leaf wilting, nutrient deficiency, senescence, and eventually death (Pan et al., 2022; Tian et al., 2021).

Plants have evolved various acclimation responses to enhance survival in flooded soils. Waterlogging can trigger local survival responses but also lead to shoot-specific acclimation responses (Parent et al., 2008; Visser and Voesenek, 2005). The internal changes caused within plant roots due to restricted gas diffusion are harmful but can also serve as important stress signals triggering vital acclimation responses. This includes oxygen decline, ROS, and NO generation but also the quick accumulation of ethylene. Due to its gaseous nature, ethylene builds up to very high levels in flooded roots due to physical entrapment. It has emerged as an early flood-warning cue mediating the regulation of many flood-adaptive morphological and metabolic strategies (Khan et al., 2020; Sasidharan, 2022).

2. Sensing (root) flooding

Roots in flooded soils rapidly experience hypoxia and ethylene

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Fig. 1. Low oxygen and ethylene sensing in plants. A general overview of oxygen and ethylene dynamics in non-flooded and root-flooded (waterlogged) plants. In the presence of oxygen and nitric oxide (NO), plant cysteine oxidases (PCOs) mediate the oxidation of ETHYLENE RESPONSIVE FACTORS (ERFVII) of their N-terminus Cys (C^{*}). Subsequently, the PROTEOLYSIS6 (PRT6) N-degron pathway induces protein degradation of the ERFVII. Ethylene accumulation leads to activation of ETHYLENE INSENSITIVE2 (EIN2) by blocking the ethylene receptors followed by ERFVII stabilization through the absence of oxygen and the removal of NO by PHYTOGLOBIN (PGB1). ERFVII translocation towards the nucleus activates the transcription of hypoxia responsive genes (HRG), through ERFVII binding on the Hypoxia-Responsive Promoter Elements (HRPEs). The stabilization of ERFVII is influenced by various other signals relevant to flooding such as the sugar status via TARGET OF RAPAMYCIN (TOR; depicted as an energy symbol), ion availability via Hydraulic Conductivity of Root 1 (HCR1; depicted as an ion), calcium signaling via CALCIUM-DEPENDENT PROTEIN KINASE12 (CPK12; depicted by Ca²⁺) and ethylene.

accumulation (Fig. 1). Flood-induced changes in ethylene and oxygen have emerged as the primary stress cues mediating acclimation or adaptive responses. However, flood sensing can involve other pathways integrating and modulating flood sensing and signaling.

2.1. Oxygen sensing via Group VII ethylene response factors

Oxygen sensing in plants is proposed to involve both indirect (Schmidt et al., 2018) and direct sensing pathways. Direct sensing involves oxygen-dependent proteolysis of constitutively expressed transcriptional regulators (Licausi et al., 2020). In Arabidopsis, these transcriptional regulators are RELATED TO APETALA2.12 (RAP2.12), RAP2.2 and RAP2.3. Together with the hypoxia-inducible HYPOXIA RESPONSIVE1 (HRE1) and HRE2, they form the group VII ethylene response factor (ERFVII) transcription factor (TF) family (Bui et al., 2015; Licausi et al., 2010). Besides hypoxia, ethylene also influences HRE2 and RAP2.2 expression (Hess et al., 2011; Licausi et al., 2010).

The oxygen lability of the ERFVII is related to a conserved amino acid sequence in their amino terminus. This makes them targets for a ubiquitin-dependent N-degron proteolytic pathway, comprising a series of post-translational modifications during normoxia, starting with the oxidation of their N-terminus Cys (Nt-Cys) residue by plant cysteine oxidases (PCOs). NO is one of the factors influencing this oxidation, but its functional position in the PCO branch of the PROTEOLYSIS6 (PRT6) N-degron pathway is currently unknown (Fig. 1) (Gibbs et al., 2014; Holdsworth et al., 2020). As oxygen levels decline, ERFVII stabilization and nuclear relocation occur triggering activation of a core set of

hypoxia response genes (HRGs) (Gibbs et al., 2011; Licausi et al., 2011). This re-localization of RAP2.12 and activation of HRGs can already occur when oxygen levels decrease towards ten percent (Kosmacz et al., 2015; Gibbs et al., 2014; Holdsworth et al., 2020).

Additionally, the carbohydrate status of the plant and ion availability have proven to be important factors influencing the stabilization of ERFVII. Plants sync the hypoxia response with their energy status via the master energy sensor, *Target of rapamycin* (TOR). Optimal sugar levels stimulate TOR (Kunkowska et al., 2023) HRG activation. Suboptimal sugar levels inactivate TOR and dampen RAP2.12 activity (Fig. 1) (Kunkowska et al., 2023). The consequent reduction in (Shahzad et al., 2016) to conserve energy when fermentable sugars are unavailable. Comparably, *Hydraulic Conductivity of Root 1* (HCR1) integrates cation availability and oxygen sensing via the phosphorylation of RAP2.12. This controls the activation of HRGs followed by direct or indirect suppression of aquaporin activity, ultimately influencing root hydraulics (Fig. 1) (Shahzad et al., 2016).

In addition to direct N-degron mediated direct oxygen sensing mechanism, it has also been suggested that oxygen decline can be indirectly sensed. These potential mechanisms include changes in hypoxia-induced redox status (NADH/ NAD⁺), or ROS production (Liu et al., 2022), or NO sensing through hemoglobins (Borisjuk and Rolletschek, 2008; Sasidharan and Mustruph, 2011). It is hypothesized that the availability of potassium (K⁺) might also be a signal referencing the saturation status of the soil during flooding and controlling plant growth in response to the stress. Calcium signaling also plays an important role in plant hypoxia responses. A regulatory model of calcium-dependent

Fig. 2. Escape and coping mechanisms to waterlogging conditions. (A) During waterlogging, ethylene and H_2O_2 orchestrate epidermal cell death near the Adventitious Root (AR) primordia, benefiting AR emergence. (B) Lysigenous aerenchyma is generated by targeted cell death of cortical cells, driven by ethylene-mediated ROS activation as a response to deal with insufficient gas exchange. (C) Ethylene accumulation during waterlogging leads to the repression of genes involved in normal root growth and development, thus allowing the plant to allocate its energy and resources in withstanding anaerobic conditions. (D) Energy-saving mechanisms mediated by ethylene involves the repression of protein translation of transcripts involved in energetically expensive processes. This occurs through ethylene-mediated noncanonical pathways to activate GNC2, leading to repression in GTP conversion and general translational processes.

protein kinase 12 (CPK12) and ERFVIs has been proposed in which CPK12 is rapidly activated in the cytoplasm during hypoxia and transported in its phosphorylated state towards the nucleus where ERFVIs are phosphorylated (Fig. 1) (Fan et al., 2023). This all suggests the potential presence of multiple flood detection cues, in addition to ethylene, for acclimation to the stress.

2.2. Other putative direct oxygen sensing mechanisms

It is currently unclear where oxygen sensing occurs and if there are additional unidentified oxygen sensors. Wang and colleagues (2017) propose soil hypoxia sensing occurs in plant cells at the interface with the external environment (Wang et al., 2017b; Wang et al., 2017a). The plasma membrane of the root epidermal cells senses external changes in oxygen levels; or the cells located at the xylem parenchyma boundary, where the lowest oxygen pressure can be experienced. Several alternative putative plant oxygen sensors have been proposed, such as ion channels and proteins containing a putative heme-based oxygen-sensing domain. Interestingly, among these putative plant oxygen-sensing proteins containing such domains is the phytochrome (PHY) family of photoreceptors, and the blue light photoreceptor Phototropin 1 (PHOT1) and PHOT2. How these photoreceptors are integrated in the grand scheme of oxygen sensing is unknown, but light perception and oxygen sensing have been demonstrated to aid successful seedling establishment following germination (Abbas et al., 2015).

2.3. Ethylene dynamics and signaling

Ethylene build-up in flooded tissues due to its physical entrapment is considered a reliable flood warning signal (Banga et al., 1996). This occurs rapidly and likely prior to a significant drop in oxygen levels.

Ethylene biosynthesis involves the conversion of the amino acid methionine to S-adenosyl-methionine (SAM) by SAM synthase, followed by the formation of 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid (ACC) by ACC synthase (ACS). The ethylene precursor ACC is then oxidized by ACC oxidase (ACO), to finally produce ethylene (Houben and Van de Poel, 2019; Pattyn et al., 2021). After production, ethylene diffuses throughout the plant and induces ethylene-mediated responses by binding to ethylene receptors (ETHYLENE RESPONSE 1 (ETR1), ETHYLENE RESPONSE SENSOR 1 (ERS1), ETR2, ERS2 and ETHYLENE INSENSITIVE 4 (EIN4)) located at the membrane of the endoplasmic reticulum (ER). This binding blocks the receptors leading to a conformational change of CONSTITUTIVE TRIPLE RESPONSE 1 (CTR1), which reduces EIN2 ubiquitination and subsequent proteolysis. Increased EIN2 levels lead to the activation of the TFs EIN3 and EIN3-LIKE1 (EIL1) and induction of target ETHYLENE RESPONSE FACTORS (ERFs), which trigger ethylene responses. Besides this canonical ethylene-signaling pathway, a non-canonical pathway induces ethylene responses independently of CTR1, EIN2, EIN3/EIL1 and ERFs. However, this route is not fully understood yet (Bakshi et al., 2018; Binder, 2020).

Ethylene dynamics can be influenced as oxygen levels start to decline. Hypoxia can stimulate ethylene biosynthesis through the up-regulation of ACS and ACOs (Banga et al., 1996; Khan et al., 2020; Pan et al., 2022; Voesenek and Sasidharan, 2013). In Arabidopsis seedlings, a short-term 3% hypoxia treatment induced the expression of ACS2, ACS6 and ACS7, stimulating ethylene biosynthesis in the root and shoot (Peng et al., 2005). Recently, Eun and colleagues (2019) demonstrated that submergence induces ACS11 expression (Eun et al., 2019). In tomato, however, long-term waterlogging stimulated ethylene sensing rather than ethylene biosynthesis by increasing ETHYLENE RECEPTOR 1 (ETR1) and ETR3 expression (Horchani and Aschi-Smiti, 2011). Less is known regarding the effect of hypoxia on ACOs. An

exception is the hypoxia inducible Arabidopsis *ACO1*, which part of the well-established cohort of 49 core HRGs (Mustroph et al., 2009; Safavi-Rizi et al., 2020). ACC synthesis is considered the rate-limiting step in ethylene biosynthesis because rapid ethylene production is induced by ACC treatment. Nevertheless, several studies have shown that ACC oxidation by ACOs can be the rate-limiting step controlling ethylene biosynthesis (Houben and Van de Poel, 2019). For example, in *Rumex palustris*, an increase in ACO counterbalanced the reduced enzyme activity caused by hypoxia and therefore affected ethylene biosynthesis (Vriezen et al., 1999). A recent study investigated the potential of creating flood-tolerant plants by overexpressing ACOs. These overexpressors were more tolerant in comparison to the wild-type, but more research is required to elucidate the pathway enhancing survival during flooding (Ramadoss et al., 2018).

Besides hypoxia, NO and ROS can also affect ethylene biosynthesis. NO influences ethylene biosynthesis via post-translational modification of ACS and ACO proteins (Mur et al., 2015; Zafari et al., 2022). In relation to ROS, waterlogging induces an NADPH oxidase gene *AtRboh D* that positively regulates hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) production and *ADH1* gene expression (Sun et al., 2018). The *atrboh d* mutant revealed that it regulates ethylene biosynthesis through *ACS7* and *ACS8*, and HRGs (Yang and Hong, 2015).

3. Ethylene-mediated root survival responses

Upon local stress perception in the roots, ethylene mediates several root adaptive responses to flooding (Fig. 2). These include morphological changes such as adventitious root and aerenchyma formation that are designed to promote internal aeration and thus 'escape' hypoxia. Others include metabolic changes that permit 'coping' with hypoxia and its consequences. This includes a reduction in growth and repression of energetically expensive processes to restore energy balance and ROS amelioration to cope with (post-) hypoxic injury.

3.1. Hypoxia escape mechanisms

Plants can escape hypoxia by developing primary aerenchyma in the cortical cells, forming internal gas cavities to enhance oxygen diffusion through the plant to maintain aerobic respiration in submerged roots and better survive waterlogging (Armstrong, 1980; Evans, 2004; Voesenek et al., 2006; Yamauchi et al., 2013). Lysed cells also mean less energy consumption for root maintenance. Lysigenous aerenchyma are induced by ethylene, showcasing an interesting cell-type specific effect in the cortex even though ethylene accumulates in all root cells during waterlogging (Colmer et al., 2006; Sasidharan et al., 2018; Yamauchi et al., 2014, 2019). In rice, ethylene enhances ROS through the activation of Respiratory Burst Oxidase Homolog (RBOH) gene (also known as NADPH oxidase), specifically *RBOHH*, to promote cell death for aerenchyma formation (Fig. 2B) (Yamauchi et al., 2018). Wheat has a similar mechanism, but additionally hypoxia-induced NO stimulates ethylene production by regulating *ACS* and *ACO* while also modulating ROS through mediation of NADPH oxidase transcript (Wany et al., 2017; Yamauchi et al., 2014). An ethylene-independent activation of RBOH also occurs via calcium-dependent protein kinases (CDPK), in which an influx of Ca^{2+} from the apoplast triggered by oxygen deficiency signals CDPKs to initiate RBOH phosphorylation and in turn mediates ROS production for inducible aerenchyma formation (Yamauchi and Nakazono, 2022).

Although ethylene-independent in its formation, another important factor in the plant's internal aeration during low oxygen conditions is the radial oxygen loss (ROL) barrier. As oxygen diffuses in the root and travels towards the root tip, it can be consumed in root cells or lost radially as it dispels in the rhizosphere (Yamauchi et al., 2018). ROL barrier is formed by cell wall changes at the exodermis, mainly suberin accumulation, and works in parallel with aerenchyma to better distribute oxygen across the root (Ejiri and Shiono, 2019; Pedersen et al.,

2021; Yamauchi et al., 2018).

Another escape strategy involving ethylene is adventitious roots (AR) growth. While AR are a normal occurrence in many different plant species as part of their standard root development, they are an important flood-adaptive response in several plant species such as tomato, *Rumex*, and rice (Steffens and Rasmussen, 2016). Aerenchyma rich ARs help the plant survive waterlogging by facilitating gas transport through these air spaces. Furthermore, AR can grow upwardly to reach better lit and aerated conditions (Lin and Sauter, 2018) and can also develop photosynthetically active chloroplasts, allowing the possibility of internally sourcing oxygen (Rich et al., 2008, 2011; Steffens and Rasmussen, 2016).

Upon waterlogging, ethylene and H_2O_2 mediate cell death at the epidermal cells covering the root primordium (Fig. 2A) (Mergemann and Sauter, 2000; Steffens and Sauter, 2009). In tomato, flooding-induced AR generation requires both auxin accumulation and ethylene synthesis, whereas upon hypoxia treatment, no ARs are formed and ethylene levels are also reduced (Negi et al., 2010; Vidoz et al., 2010). In cucumber, AR formation by auxin requires ethylene, whereas ethylene is capable of inducing AR by itself in an auxin-independent way. AR formation in both cases requires mediation by ROS (Qi et al., 2019). Interestingly, in rice, AR primordia are normally already formed even before stress induction, and the generation of stress signals triggers their emergence and growth (Mergemann and Sauter, 2000).

AR formation is also known to involve the ERFVIs. In *Zea mays* (maize) the waterlogging-responsive gene *ZmEREB180* was identified as a member of the *ZmERFVII* gene family and was up-regulated by ethylene. Overexpression of *ZmEREB180* in maize seedlings enhanced the survival rate after long-term waterlogging stress through the stimulation of AR formation and regulation of antioxidant levels (Yu et al., 2019). On the other hand, in rice, Lin and colleagues (2022) found a potential connection between *SNORKEL1* (*SK1*) and *SK2* (both ERFs) and the formation of two different types of AR differing in their anatomical and morphological traits, as well as emergence timing. It remains to be elucidated whether *SK1* and *SK2* are responsible and if this is mediated by ethylene the same way as it is in deepwater rice (Lin et al., 2022).

3.2. Hypoxia coping mechanisms

Some species are unable to adapt by enhancing internal aeration to ameliorate the negative effects of hypoxia. Instead, hypoxia coping mechanisms can prolong root survival, where ethylene mediates metabolic adjustments to low-oxygen conditions. In keeping with the hierarchy of ethylene accumulation and oxygen decline during flooding, an ethylene pre-treatment was found to improve tolerance to subsequent hypoxia in *Rumex palustris* and Arabidopsis (Hartman et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2022). This beneficial effect of ethylene involves the modulation of a range of processes that allow hypoxic acclimation. Repressing growth and energetically expensive processes can enhance plant survival (H. Zhang et al., 2020). Since hypoxia impairs ATP production this can contribute towards the maintenance of energy homeostasis and prolong survival. In Arabidopsis seedlings, ethylene exposure caused transcriptome reconfiguration associated with a general downregulation of growth and energetically expensive processes. This included down-regulation of cell maintenance, development, cell cycle, growth stimulation, and brassinosteroid biosynthesis, among others. Repression of root growth was suggested to be regulated by the down-regulation of several developmental regulators including *PLT1*, *PLT2*, *SCR1*, *SHR*, *TCP21* and *SHY2* (Fig. 2C). On the other hand, expression of genes related to ABA biosynthesis (growth suppressor), and stress-related genes like *PGB1*, *ADH1*, *HRE1* and *RAP2.3*, was upregulated (Liu et al., 2022).

Ethylene enhances the production of *PGB1*, within an hour, through the activation of EIN2 and EIN3/EIL1 dependent signaling. The increase in *PGB1* and consequent reduction in NO levels limits targeted

proteolysis of the RAP-type ERV1 TFs via the PRT6-N-degron pathway. Subsequently, stabilized ERV1s are translocated to the nucleus where, only when oxygen deprivation occurs, HRGs are induced (Hartman et al., 2020; Perata, 2020). Interestingly there seems to be some variation in this beneficial ethylene effect trait. While it was present in a waterlogging-tolerant potato cultivar of *Solanum tuberosum*, it was lost in the waterlogging-sensitive cultivar. PGB1 also contributes to ethylene-mediated amelioration of ROS formed during hypoxia and subsequent re-oxygenation (Liu et al., 2022).

Ethylene has also been demonstrated to modulate translation (Cho et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022). Cho and colleagues (2022) linked ethylene-induced translational repression to EIN2 and General control nonderepressible 2 (GCN2). Ethylene activates GCN2 during light submergence noncanonically, which in turn phosphorylates eukaryotic initiation factor 2 α (eIF2 α) resulting in a stop of conversion from GDP to GTP, arresting general translation (Fig. 2D). Additionally, overexpression of GCN2 enhanced submergence tolerance by retaining higher ATP and NAD⁺ levels, suggesting that GCN2 plays a role in controlling energy balance during submergence. On this note, Lee and Bailey-Serres (2019) presented evidence that, during hypoxia, abundant transcripts are compartmentalized in the nucleus, which assists with energy conservation by limiting translation (Lee and Bailey-Serres, 2019). Transcripts in this compartmentalization (nuclear retention and cytoplasmic sequestration) can be easily accessed upon re-oxygenation enabling rapid restoration of essential molecular processes for recovery.

4. To breathe or not to breathe: the dual role of ethylene during waterlogging and stress recovery

Plant survival in floods not only relies on early stress signaling but also on the effectiveness of recovery mechanisms upon reoxygenation. Tissue re-aeration after flooding leads to a burst in ROS production, caused by the high energetic demands of reactivated mitochondria and chloroplasts, and a limited scavenging capacity (Sasidharan et al., 2018; Yeung et al., 2018; Yuan et al., 2023). Excessive ROS accumulation can disrupt redox homeostasis, and lead to damage of cell membranes, nucleic acids and proteins, resulting in further tissue dehydration and increased senescence at the early stages of recovery (Chaki et al., 2020).

Ethylene plays a pivotal role in reoxygenation acclimation responses. Congruently, reoxygenation induces a strong upregulation of several genes involved in ethylene biosynthesis (e.g. ACS and ACO enzymes), signaling (EBF2, ERS1), and response (e.g. ERF1 and ERF2). Noteworthy is the upregulation of these genes in a gene- and time-specific pattern, suggesting tight regulation of ethylene biosynthesis and signaling (Tsai et al., 2014).

Our understanding of plant reoxygenation responses has increased considerably in recent years. Reoxygenation following hypoxia triggers a fast (30 mins-1hr) and strong transcriptional reprogramming in Arabidopsis seedlings (Liu et al., 2022; Tsai et al., 2014, 2016). This includes the induction of genes encoding ROS scavengers, ion transport, amino acid breakdown, and replenishment of the TCA cycle. Subsequently, plants reactivate the translation of proteins related to energy-demanding processes such as cell division, cell-wall biosynthesis, and growth in general (Liu et al., 2022; Tsai et al., 2014, 2016; L. Wang et al., 2016). Ethylene directly contributes to these acclimations in an ERV1-dependent and -independent manner, thus suggesting that ethylene and hypoxia signaling converge, to a certain extent, during reoxygenation responses (Hartman et al., 2021). In agreement, the beneficial effects of ethylene in hypoxia recovery are related to enhanced antioxidant capacity in roots, mediated to a great extent by ethylene-mediated upregulation of PGB1, RAP2.2, and RAP2.12. Ethylene-enhanced antioxidant capacity also includes the upregulation of peroxidases such as ascorbate peroxidase (Liu et al., 2022). Future research is needed to establish the molecular network activated by PGB1 and ERV1s to ameliorate oxidative stress during reoxygenation.

Ethylene plays a pivotal role in reestablishing hormonal balance and

plant survival during reoxygenation. Transcriptomic analyses on *ein3eil1* seedlings showed that ethylene signaling is crucial for inducing Jasmonic Acid (JA) biosynthesis and signaling shortly after reoxygenation. Furthermore, *ein3eil1* mutants displayed enhanced expression of ABA biosynthesis and signaling genes, making ethylene the signaling hub steering hormone responses during reoxygenation (Tsai et al., 2014).

Ethylene can also mitigate dehydration stress during post-flooding recovery. This is related to the ethylene-dependent upregulation of DEHYDRATION RESPONSIVE ELEMENT BINDING, DRE1A and DRE1B, and several HEAT SHOCK FACTORS, including HSF2, and HEAT SHOCK PROTEINS, Hsp17.6, Hsp21 and HSP70 (Tsai et al., 2014).

Metabolic acclimations for enhancing N and C assimilation during recovery are also key during flooding stress recovery. Conversion of amino acids and fermentation byproducts for replenishment of glycolysis and the TCA cycle intermediates is crucial in this process. Additionally, TCA replenishment can also increase ROS scavenging capacity as several of the byproducts in these reactions can be oxidized. Fermentation byproducts, such as ethanol and lactic acid, can be toxic when accumulating. Plants have evolved strategies to reduce this accumulation by converting pyruvate and Glu into 2-oxoglutarate (2OG), and benign amino acids such as Alanine (Ala). This reaction is reversibly mediated by the Alanine aminotransferase, AlaAT. Reoxygenation leads to increased Ala breakdown as a means of TCA cycle replenishment through its conversion into pyruvate. GDH, a glutamine dehydrogenase that acts as a cofactor of AlaAT, enhances reoxygenation recovery by regulating sugar metabolism and phytosterol synthesis. Interestingly GDH2 is directly targeted by EIN3 thus implying a direct role of ethylene signaling in this process (Tsai et al., 2016). Alternatively, ethylene can also mediate the replenishment of the TCA cycle by inducing the expression of enzymes involved in the Glutathione-Ascorbic acid (AA) pathway, a well-known mechanism for mitigating ROS accumulation (Hasanuzzaman et al., 2019).

Waterlogging-induced molecular responses in crops have focused largely on early signaling responses rather than on subsequent acclimations during recovery. Transcriptomic analyses in sesame and peony stand out in this regard and support the importance of ROS amelioration in waterlogging recovery (L. Wang et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2022b; Zhang et al., 2022a). In addition, PGB1 expression positively correlates with waterlogging resilience in maize and soybean (Hammond et al., 2020; Mira et al., 2021; Youssef et al., 2016). Furthermore, exogenous ethylene treatment can also lead to enhanced waterlogging survival in soybean, thus indicating that core recovery mechanisms are rather conserved in different plant species (Kim et al., 2018).

5. Long-distance signaling – the road towards distant acclimation responses in the shoot

Flooded roots can also affect the growth and development of the aerial parts of the plant. This effect is likely to be accommodated by a root-derived long-distance signal. Despite lacking a nervous system, plants can still communicate long-distance through the vascular system to induce shoot acclimation responses.

5.1. 1-Aminocyclopropane 1-Carboxylic Acid (ACC) as a systemic signal

The most well-known ethylene-related mechanism of long-distance signaling is the transport of its precursor ACC through the xylem towards the shoot. This waterlogging-induced mechanism was studied in the tomato species *Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill. cv. VFN8 by Jackson and colleagues during the mid-seventies (Jackson and Campbell, 1976). In waterlogged hypoxic roots, ethylene biosynthesis is inhibited by repression of ACO activity, leading to ACC over-accumulation. This ACC is transported through the xylem towards the normoxic shoot where ACC oxidation fuels a surge of ethylene production. In tomato, this ethylene burst is associated with the characteristic downward bending

Fig. 3. Waterlogging induces shoot acclimation responses via ethylene and ACC. In waterlogged roots, hypoxic conditions favor the accumulation of the ethylene precursor 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid (ACC). ACC transport from the anaerobic root to the aerobic shoot can lead to ethylene (C₂H₄) production there. In the shoot, ethylene can trigger epinasty, hyponasty and stomatal closure. Hydraulic signaling is another potential mechanism for long-distance root-to-shoot signaling during waterlogging.

of petioles (epinasty) leading to droopy leaves (Fig. 3). This leaf epinasty is proposed to offset excessive transpiration losses and compensate for malfunctioning roots. Leaf epinasty is one of the remarkable examples when referring to age-dependent responses regulated by ethylene (Fig. 4). In tomato, this is a general above-ground response that occurs soon after waterlogging imposition (24 and 48 h) (Geldhof et al., 2022; Jackson and Campbell, 1976), regardless of leaf age. The effect of leaf ontogeny becomes noticeable during root reoxygenation since younger leaves display faster recovery than older ones. This phenomenon is regulated through the crosstalk between ethylene and auxin. ACC transport towards the shoot occurs upon root hypoxia, especially towards the sink, young leaves. ACC accumulation in the leaves induces the expression of different ACO paralogues, which results in higher ethylene biosynthesis in old leaves, as most of the ACC allocated to young leaves, are conjugated into inactive MACC. In parallel, the reduced expression of *PIN1* and *PIN9* auxin exporters in old leaves leads

to a higher local accumulation of auxin in the petiole, increased higher adaxial-to-abaxial cell elongation and leaf bending (Geldhof et al., 2022).

The output shoot response of waterlogging can vary between species. Amongst rosette species, shoots of waterlogged plants display the opposite response i.e. an upward leaf bending (hyponasty). This has been observed in *Arabidopsis thaliana*, *Trifolium subterraneum* ssp. *yan-nanicum*, *Rumex* spp. and *Rorippa sylvestris* (Enkhbat et al., 2022; Rauf et al., 2013; Stift et al., 2008; Voesenek et al., 1990). In *Arabidopsis*, SPEEDY HYPONASTIC GROWTH (SHYG) mediates waterlogging-induced hyponasty by direct regulation of ethylene biosynthesis through ACO5 (Rauf et al., 2013). High ethylene levels initiate hyponastic growth by promoting cell elongation and simultaneously reducing A2-type CYCLIN-mediated cell proliferation (Polko et al., 2015).

Another response is the reduction in stomatal conductance which is

Fig. 4. Ethylene-mediated acclimation responses to waterlogging are influenced by internal and external factors. The mechanistic action of ethylene during waterlogging stress and recovery is determined by four main factors: natural history, stress properties, developmental and external cues. Examples of how these factors impact ethylene-mediated waterlogging responses are illustrated within the dashed boxes. (B) Ethylene resilience mediated by ACC deaminase-producing bacteria, *E. cloacae* UW4 and CAL2. ACC-deaminase is a bacterial enzyme, capable of degrading plant ACC in waterlogged roots. This results in a decrease of ACC transport to the shoot, and consequently, reduced ethylene production in aerial organs and enhanced waterlogging survival. (Grichko et al., 2001)(C) Dual role of ethylene in metabolic shifts during waterlogging and reoxygenation. Ethylene positively regulates the expression of group VII of the Ethylene Responsive Factors transcription factors, RAP2.12 and HRE2, which in turn upregulates *ADH* and *PDC* to activate fermentation at the onset of hypoxia. During recovery, conversely, ethylene promotes respiration by promoting ROS detoxification through EIN3-mediated upregulation of ERFs, and downstream activation of peroxidases and catalases. (D) Genetic variation of waterlogging responses in mungbean (*Vigna radiata*) is associated with the differential expression of ACC synthases (ACSs) and ethylene responsive factors (ERFs) (Sreeratre et al., 2022).

(A) Age-dependent hyponastic responses in waterlogged tomato plants (modified from Geldhof et al., 2022).

marked as one of the earliest shoot responses to waterlogging (Fig. 3) (Bradford and Hsiao, 1982; Schull and Thomas, 2000). Oxygen deficiency in the soil occurs within minutes and disturbs the water homeostasis within the root, often leading to a reduction of water flow through the transpiration stream (Le Provost et al., 2016; Peláez-Vico et al., 2023). The regulation of stomatal closure in response to waterlogging has been historically attributed to root-derived ABA, but grafting experiments revealed that ABA production in the leaves was enhanced independently of ABA biosynthesis in the root (Holbrook, 2002). During drought, hydraulic systemic signaling is induced by changes in water tension, turgor, and osmotic potential and sensed by an unknown sensor which then stimulates leaf ABA biosynthesis (Christmann et al., 2013). In turn, ABA regulates stomatal closure (Jackson and Campbell, 1976; Zhao et al., 2021). Stomatal closure during waterlogging might also involve ethylene, although its exact role remains unclear. In Arabidopsis, ethylene induces stomatal closure in the presence of H₂O₂ in the guard cells. Blocking ethylene perception via the application of the chemical 1-methylcyclopropene (1-MCP) interfered with ROS-mediated stomatal closure (Desikan et al., 2006). However, the application of exogenous ethylene in several plant species (e.g. Arabidopsis, tomato, and sunflower) resulted in the inhibition of

ABA-induced stomatal closure (Benlloch-González et al., 2010; Holbrook, 2002; Tanaka et al., 2005). It is suggested that, independently, ethylene or ABA promote stomatal closure, but when present together they act as antagonists (Chen et al., 2022). This antagonism is demonstrated in Arabidopsis in the context of re-oxygenation after submergence, where ABA and ethylene signaling interact through *SENESCENCE-ASSOCIATED GENE113* (SAG113) and *ORESARA1* (ORE1) to control stomatal opening (Yeung et al., 2018).

Recent studies suggest that ACC itself can act as a signaling molecule triggering direct effects independent of ethylene or through the interaction with ethylene signaling (Mou et al., 2020; Vanderstraeten et al., 2019). The *acs* octuple mutant produced shorter siliques and fewer seeds in comparison with the wild-type, but this phenotype is absent in ethylene-insensitive mutants suggesting a specific role of ACC in ovule development (Mou et al., 2020). Even though this finding was unrelated to flooding, it is possible that root-derived ACC during flooding mediates shoot effects. Tools such as the development of Arabidopsis mutant lines incapable of producing ethylene, and identification of ACC transporters, should facilitate exploration of the specific role of ACC in waterlogging, either as a systemic signal upregulating ethylene biosynthesis and/or as an independent signaling molecule (Choi et al., 2019; Heydlauff et al.,

Table 1

Genome-wide studies of waterlogging stress responses in different plant species. Information regarding species, approaches, developmental states, and waterlogging stress conditions are specified. *Single Molecule, Real-Time sequencing. Abbreviations: mw: minutes of waterlogging, hw: hours of waterlogging, dw: days of waterlogging and ww: weeks of waterlogging. Recovery timepoints are abbreviated similarly, using R instead of w. Dashes within cells indicate unspecified information.

Species	Common name	Approach	Tissue	Purpose	Age	Set up	Time points	Reference	doi
<i>Actinidia valvata</i>	kiwifruit	SMRT RNA-seq	Roots	Transcriptomic responses	5–6 leaf stage	Pots in tank, 2–3 cm above soil surface	0, 12, 24 and 72 hw	Li et al. (2022)	10.3390/ijms23063237
<i>Actinidia valvata</i> and <i>Actinidia deliciosa</i>	kiwifruit	RNA-seq	Roots	Comparison between species	-	-	2, 4dw	Gao et al., 2022	10.1016/j.gene.2022.146843
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	Thale cress	RNA-seq	Roots	Comparison Col-0 and <i>rbhd</i> mutants	4-week old	Peat pellets, full saturation	0, 10, 30, 60mw	Peláez-Vico et al. (2023)	10.1101/2023.03.22.533859
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	Thale cress	Microarrays	Shoots and Roots	Comparison Col-0 and <i>ein2-5</i> mutants	14-day old	Plants on foamed plastic strips, 3% oxygen (N2 bombing)	0, 0.5, 3, 6 hw	Hsu et al., 2011	10.1371/journal.pone.0028888
<i>Arachis hypogaea L.</i>	Peanut	Proteomics	Roots	Comparison between cultivars	4 leaf stage	PVC basins	12dw	Liu et al., 2021	10.3389/fpls.2021.716114
<i>Brassica napus</i>	Rape	RNA-seq	Shoot	Transcriptomic responses	2 leaf stage	Pots in tanks, 1 cm above soil surface	36hw-3dw	Lee et al., 2014	10.1007/s00299-013-1529-8
<i>Cerasus sachalinensis</i>	Cherry tree	RNA-seq	Roots	Transcriptomic responses	10–12 leaf stage	Pots in tanks, 3 cm above soil surface	3 h, 6 h, and 24 hw	Zhang t al., 2017	10.1186/s12864-017-4055-1
<i>Chrysanthemum morifolium</i>	florist's daisy	RNA-seq	Roots	Comparison between cultivars	10–12 leaf stage	Individual pots (2,5 cm above soil surface)	0 hw, 12 hw, and 2hR	Zhao et al., 2018	10.3390/ijms19051455
<i>Cucumis sativus</i>	Cucumber	Proteomics	hypocotyls	Comparison between cultivars	three leaf stage	Individual pots (ca. 4cms above soil surface)	2dw	Xu et al., 2016	10.3389/fpls.2016.01515
<i>Cucumis sativus</i>	Cucumber	RNA-seq (focus on lncRNAs)	Roots	Comparison between cultivars	21-days after cultivation	Pots in tanks, 4–7 cm above soil surface	0dw, 7dW, 14dR, 7dW (primmed plants)	Keska et al. 2021	10.3390/genes12020189
<i>Eragrostis tef</i>	Tef	RNA-seq	Roots	Transcriptomic responses	19-day old	Pots in tanks, 1 cm above soil surface	9dw	Cannarozzi et al., 2018	10.1002/pld3.56
<i>Glycine max</i>	Soybean	GWAS	Leaves	Comparison between cultivars	V2 stage	Polyvinyl chloride tubes	-	kim et al., 2023	10.3390/ijms24010873
<i>Glycine max</i>	Soybean	Proteomics	roots	Proteomic responses	V2 stage	Pots, 2 cm above the soil surface	3dw, 7dw	Alam et al., 2010	10.1007/s12038-010-0007-5
<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	Cotton	RNA-seq	Leaves	Transcriptomic responses	flowering stage	Plots, 20 cm above soil surface	15dW	Zhang t al., 2017	10.1371/journal.pone.0185075
<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	Cotton	Microarrays	Leaves and roots	Transcriptomic responses	2-leaf stage	Plastic tubs, 1 cm above soil surface	4hw(roots), 24hw(leaves)	Christianson et al., 2009	10.1093/pcp/pcp163
<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	Barley	GWAS	Leaves	Comparison between cultivars	2–3 leaf stage	Pots in tanks	-	Manik et al., 2022	10.3390/ijms23063341
<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	Barley	RNA-seq	Root	Comparison between cultivars	2-week old seedlings	Plants in cone-tainer cells	0dw, 3dw	Borrego-Benjumea et al., 2020	10.3390/plants9020240
<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	Barley	GWAS	Leaves	Comparison between cultivars	3-leaf stage	-	-	Zhang et al., 2017	10.1007/s00122-017-2910-8
<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	Barley	Proteomics	Leaves, roots (adventitious, nodal, and seminal)	Comparison between cultivars	4-week stage	PVC basins, 2–3 cm above soil surface	3ww	Luan et al., 2018	10.1038/s41598-018-27726-1
<i>Jatropha curca</i>	Jatropha	RNA-seq	Roots	Transcriptomic responses	6 leaf stage	Pots in tanks, 3 cm above soil surface	1dW	Juntawong et al., 2014	10.3389/fpls.2014.00658
<i>M. acuminata</i>	Banana	RNA-seq	Roots	Transcriptomic responses	2-month old	Individual pots (2 cm above soil surface)	1dw	Yang Teoh et al., 2022	10.3390/plants11152052
<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cassava	RNA-seq	Leaves and roots	Transcriptomic responses	45 days after transplanting	Pots in tanks, 3–4 cm above soil surface	6dw	Cao et al., 2022	10.1371/journal.pone.0261086
<i>Paeonia ostii</i>	Peony	SMRT RNA-seq	Root	Transcriptomic responses	3-year-old	Pots in tanks, 2 cm above soil surface	3dw-7dR	Zhang et al. (2022b); Zhang et al. (2022a)	10.3389/fpls.2022.1030584

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Species	Common name	Approach	Tissue	Purpose	Age	Set up	Time points	Reference	doi
<i>Phalaris arundinacea</i>	Reed canary grass	RNA-seq	Leaves and roots	Comparison between cultivars	2-week old	Pots, 10 cm above soil surface	6ww	Wang et al., 2021	10.1016/j.jplph.2021.153428
<i>Quercus robur</i>	Oak	RNA-seq	stem	Comparison between species	5-week-old	Pots in tanks, 2 cm above collar roots	9dw	Le Provost et al. (2016)	10.1093/treephys/tpw056
<i>Sesamum indicum</i>	Sesame	RNA-seq	Roots	Comparison between cultivars	flowering stage	-	0, 3, 9 15 hw and 20 hR	Wang et al. (2016)	10.1371/journal.pone.0149912
<i>Sesamum indicum</i>	Sesame	RNA-seq	Roots	Transcriptomic responses	Anthesis	-	9hw	Wang et al., 2012	10.1007/s11738-012-1024-9
<i>Sesbania cannabina</i>	Sesbania	RNA-seq	Roots	Transcriptomic responses	30 day old plants	Pots in tanks	3 h, 27hw	Ren et al., 2017	10.1038/s41598-017-07740-5
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	Tomato	RNA-seq	Roots	Transcriptomic analyses	5 week old plants	Hydroponics, N2 gas	6hw, 48hw	Safavi-Rizi et al., 2022	10.1038/s41598-020-57884-0
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	Tomato	Proteomics	Leaves	Proteomic responses	5 week old plants	Pots in tanks, 2 cm above soil surface	24, 48, 72hw	Ahsan et al., 2007	10.1111/j.1399-3054.2007.00980.x
<i>Taxodium 'Zhongshansa'</i>	Hybrid cypress	RNA-seq	Shoots and roots	Transcriptomic responses	2-week old plants	Pots in tanks	1hw	Qi et al., 2014	10.1186/s12870-014-0201-y
<i>Vigna radiata</i>	Mung bean	RNA-seq	Roots	Comparison between cultivars	15 day-old, five-leaf-stage plants	Pots in tanks, 3 cm above soil surface	0, 1 and 7dW	Sreratree et al., 2022	10.3390/plants11070930
<i>Vigna vexillata</i>	Zombie pea	RNA-seq	Roots	Comparison between cultivars	Fifteen-day-old, five-leaf-stage	Pots in tanks, 3 cm above soil surface	10dw	Butsayawarapat et al., 2019	10.3390/plants8080264
<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize	RNA-seq	Roots	Transcriptomic responses (focus on lncRNAs)	2 leaf stage	Shared tank, 2–3 cm above soil surface	2 h, 4 h, 6 h, 8 h, 10 h, and 12 hw	Yu et al., 2020	10.3390/genes11030267
<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize	RNA-seq	Roots	Transcriptomic responses	8 fully expanded leaf	Individual pots, 5 cm above soil surface	15dw	Yao et al., 2021	10.1007/s12374-021-09298-2
<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize	Microarrays	Roots	Comparison between cultivars	8-days old	Individual pots, 5 cm above soil surface	0, 4, 7dw and 1wR	Thirunavukkarasu et al., 2013	10.1371/journal.pone.0070433
<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize	BSR-seq	Roots	Comparison between cultivars	-	Shared pots, 1–2 cm above soil surface	2dw	Du et al., 2017	10.3389/fpls.2017.01022
<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize	RNA-seq	roots	Transcriptomic responses	3-leaf stage	Sand chambers	12, 16, 20, 24hw	Zou et al., 2010	10.1186/1471-2229-10-189

2022; Li et al., 2022). Potentially, root-derived ACC could influence stomatal density as it facilitates the differentiation of guard mother cells (GMCs) into guard cells (GCs) in Arabidopsis leaves; or stomatal conductance via transportation via LHT2, which is highly expressed in the guard cells (Vanderstraeten and van Der Straeten, 2017; J. J. Yin et al., 2019b; D. Yin et al., 2019a). Importantly, while root-to-shoot ACC transport has been demonstrated in tomato, it remains unclear how conserved this systemic signaling mechanism is across other plant species during waterlogging. A recent study, focusing on rapid systemic responses during waterlogging, suggests that hydraulic waves, ROS, and calcium are involved in the early systemic plant responses and partially dependent on cell-to-cell signaling (Peláez-Vico et al., 2023).

6. Factors shaping ethylene-mediated responses to waterlogging stress

Ethylene action and phenotypic output is shaped by a plethora of factors, ranging from genetic to environmental. Based on current knowledge, we propose four major components that contribute to the versatility of ethylene in waterlogging responses (Fig. 4).

Plant stress responses, including ethylene-mediated acclimations to flooding stress, are developmentally regulated (Rankenberg et al., 2021; H. Zhang et al., 2020). Tissue-specific ethylene action is crucial for regulating important adaptations to submergence such as internode elongation and aerenchyma formation in rice and petiole elongation in *Rumex* (Hattori et al., 2009; Heydarian et al., 2010). For waterlogging, age-dependent responses have been reported in multiple crops and its impact on tolerance varies in a species-specific manner (Ahmed et al., 2002; Belford et al., 1980; Cannell et al., 1980; Ghobadi et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2022; Nabloussi et al., 2019; Ploschuk et al., 2018). Among these, tomato leaf epinasty is one of the few examples of age-dependent responses to waterlogging regulated by ethylene (Fig. 4A). While the role of ethylene in these processes is clear, how they are regulated in a tissue-specific manner is poorly understood.

External cues (e.g. environmental conditions, soil types) also influence ethylene-mediated acclimations to waterlogging stress. Probably one of the most unexplored areas in the field is the contribution of soil microbes. Besides the strong effect of waterlogging on soil microbial diversity and composition, studies in the field have demonstrated that waterlogging can increase the abundance of beneficial microbes (Hamonts et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2022; Tai-zhon, 2014; Taobing et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2017b; Wang et al., 2017a). In soybean, for instance, waterlogging leads to an increased abundance of nitrogen fixers and nutrient enrichers (Taobing et al., 2022). Interestingly, other bacteria can enhance waterlogging resilience by mitigating ethylene production in aerial organs (Fig. 4B). This is the case of bacteria that produce the ACC-deaminase, an enzyme that, in response to soil hypoxia, cleaves plant ACC, thereby reducing its accumulation in roots (Ali and Kim, 2018; Glick, 2005; Grichko and Glick, 2000, 2001a, 2001b). Altogether, these findings support plant-microbe coevolution of adaptive mechanisms to waterlogging- a new research perspective for enhancing waterlogging resilience (Ravanbakhsh et al., 2018).

Ethylene responses also vary over time, triggering different signaling cascades in early and late hypoxia as well as reoxygenation (Fig. 4C). While stress and recovery responses are related, the linking mechanisms remain elusive and factors such as stress duration should be considered. Duration-dependent waterlogging effects are not only linked to the accumulation of toxic compounds but also ethylene itself, which can alter redox status, induce leaf senescence and fruit abscission during waterlogging (Anee et al., 2019; Graham et al., 2012; Najeeb et al., 2018; Xiao et al., 2020; Yeung et al., 2018). Furthermore, controlling ethylene biosynthesis during waterlogging results in increased tolerance in certain cases, thus indicating that ethylene, despite being a pivotal signal, can also be detrimental when its presence is prolonged (Xiao et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2019).

Plant stress tolerance is the final output of adaptive (genetic) and

acclimation (genome plasticity) responses. Although some species like rice and *Rumex* are adapted to flooded environments (Voesenek and Bailey-Serres, 2015a), most crops, however, are susceptible to waterlogging (Voesenek and Bailey-Serres, 2015b). Nevertheless, considerable variation in flood resilience is observed both within and across species and extensive research has focused on defining underlying morphophysiological responses and traits indicative of resilience. The elucidation of the underlying mechanisms has been considerably helped with the emergence of the OMICs era. Such studies have pinpointed the importance of metabolic and detoxification processes in genetic variation to waterlogging resilience, with some being associated with ethylene synthesis and signaling (Fig. 4D). The vast repository of transcriptomic and proteomics datasets in several species (Table 1), provides an excellent base for identifying common and species-specific acclimation strategies and identifying components that explain tolerance variation.

7. Conclusion

This review aims to provide an integral outlook on ethylene-mediated responses to waterlogging stress in plants. Ethylene mediates plant responses both during waterlogging and reoxygenation, triggering molecular cascades for reprogramming plant metabolism, growth, ROS/NO detoxification, and energy allocation. Despite significant advances in the field, several questions persist. It remains to be resolved how despite its pervasive nature, ethylene-triggered processes are fine-tuned at the tissue and cell-type levels. There is increasing interest in the temporal role of ethylene including its role in stress memory in the context of flooding resilience. This is still a relatively unexplored area, yet important to consider with crops being exposed to more frequent flooding events. The nature of waterlogging stress clearly relies on long-distance signaling to ensure timely plant responses and survival. However, we still miss a broad view of xylem- and phloem-borne signals involved in systemic acclimations to waterlogging and resource allocation during waterlogging. Finally, plant stress biology is slowly extending its focus to multi-stress tolerance. Ethylene is of special interest in this aspect as it controls multiple biotic and abiotic stress responses. For example, waterlogging- and ethylene-induced *ERF2* and *RAP2.4*, render plants more tolerant to cold, salt, and drought (Phukan et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2007; J. Yin et al., 2019b; D. Yin et al., 2019a). Furthermore, ethylene-dependent waterlogging responses include the induction of proteins with important roles in heat and salt responses, providing evidence for a strong overlap in stress responses and identifying components that might confer multi-stress resilience in plants.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

All authors contributed to the conceptualization and writing of this review. Hendrika A.C.F. Leeggangers, Natalia Yaneth Rodriguez-Granados, Monika Gyöngyi Macias-Honti generated the figures and tables.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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